

Statistical analysis plan

Emulation of Cardiovascular Outcomes in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes: A Comparative Study of GLP-1 Receptor Agonists and DPP-4 Inhibitors Using Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) Data – Insights from the LEADER Trial

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Contents

1. Target Trial Emulation	3
1.1 Designing a target trial.....	3
1.2 Components of target trial protocol	3
2. Overview of LEADER trial.....	5
3. Trial Emulation Study Design	6
3.1 Study population	6
3.2 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria.....	7
4. Study duration and follow-ups.....	10
5. Treatment of interest	10
6. Outcome(s).....	10
7. Variable selection.....	11
8. Potential confounders.....	11
9. Data preparation.....	12
10. Analysis.....	13
10.1 Target parameter of interest	13
10.2 Descriptive analysis	13
10.3 Longitudinal Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (LTMLE)	13
10.4 Subgroup and sensitivity analysis	14
10.5 supplementary analysis	15
11. Appendix.....	16
References:.....	17

1. Target Trial Emulation

Randomised trials are the gold standard for evaluating the effectiveness and safety of interventions due to their ability to minimise bias through randomisation. However, these trials can be prohibitively expensive, unethical, or time-consuming, making them impractical in certain scenarios. In such cases, observational data can serve as an alternative to answer similar research questions[1].

The design of observational studies is critical; incorrect choices, such as improper specification of the start of follow-up, can introduce self-inflicted biases. Ensuring the validity of findings from observational data requires meticulous attention to study design and analytical methods to mitigate these biases. Despite these challenges, when executed properly, observational studies can provide important insights into the effectiveness of interventions, especially in situations where randomised trials are not feasible[2].

Explicitly defining the protocol of the target trial before emulating it using observational data is crucial for avoiding common design pitfalls. For instance, observational studies that include prevalent users of a treatment are prone to selection bias. This type of bias occurs when participants who had already started the treatment before the follow-up period are included in the active arm of the study. These participants must have survived and remained event-free (assuming no history of the outcome event is part of the eligibility criteria) while receiving treatment up until the follow-up begins. Consequently, those who initiate treatment and survive this arbitrary period tend to be artificially healthy, leading to biased results[3].

1.1 Designing a target trial

The first step in using observational data to emulate a randomised trial is to specify the protocol of the ideal trial that would have been conducted, considering the constraints of the available data. This involves defining several key elements: eligibility criteria for participants, the treatment strategies to be compared, the procedures for assigning these treatments, the outcomes to be measured, the duration and methods of follow-up, the causal contrasts of interest, and the statistical analysis plan. In this context, the target trial must be designed as a pragmatic trial, which is more flexible and reflective of real-world conditions than a placebo-controlled trial. This is because observational data inherently lack the controlled environment of a placebo group[4].

1.2 Components of target trial protocol

Successful emulation of a target trial requires a proper definition of **time zero** of follow-up in the observational data, also referred to as baseline. **Eligibility criteria** need to be met at that point but not later; study outcomes begin to be counted after that point but not earlier.[5]

In our target trial, the natural start of follow-up will be the time when the **treatment strategy** is assigned, which often occurs either shortly before or at the same time as initiation of the treatment strategy.

Follow-up should start when eligibility criteria are met, treatment strategies are assigned, and outcomes begin to be counted. Follow-up continues until the earliest occurrence of an outcome, censoring, death, competing events, or end of follow-up.

Causal parameter of Interest:

The primary causal contrasts in randomised trials are often the intention-to-treat (ITT) effect and the per-protocol effect. The ITT effect compares treatment strategies assigned at baseline regardless of subsequent adherence, while the per-protocol effect assesses the effect of fully adhering to the assigned treatment strategies. Both effects are valuable and can be estimated in observational studies if appropriate data and methodologies are available.

Intention-to-Treat Analysis

In randomised trials, the ITT effect is straightforward to estimate, as treatment assignment is random and adherence is not considered. However, emulating this in observational studies is challenging. One approach is to use prescription data to designate treatment assignment for the entire follow-up period based on the first prescription. Another strategy is to compare treatment initiators, considering patients "treated" or "untreated" based on the first treatment initiated, regardless of long-term adherence. Both approaches require adjustments for baseline confounding to balance patient characteristics between treatment groups. [6]

Per-Protocol Analysis

The per-protocol approach, in contrast, accounts for nonadherence by evaluating the comparative effectiveness of treatments that patients adhered to within randomised groups. This approach is particularly useful in noninferiority trials or when assessing treatment safety. Estimating the per-protocol effect requires adjustments for both baseline and postbaseline confounding, as postbaseline prognostic factors can influence adherence and be affected by prior adherence.[3, 7]

In emulating this target trial using Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) data, we will define the treatment strategy as "**taking active/comparator therapy continuously during the follow-up, unless otherwise clinically indicated.**" To estimate the per-protocol effect, we will consider three essential points:[7]

- Non-Censoring for Clinical Discontinuation: Data from participants who stop treatment for clinical reasons, such as side effects, should not be censored as they are not deviating from the protocol.
- Censoring for Uncertain Treatment: Data should be censored when it is no longer certain that participants are receiving the treatment.
- Adjustment for Incomplete Adherence: Adjustments must be made for confounding due to incomplete adherence.

Methodological Considerations

For ITT analysis, standard methods are used to adjust for baseline covariates. In per-protocol analysis, participants deviating from the treatment strategy are censored, and advanced methods such as g-methods [8], or Targeted maximum likelihood [9] are used to adjust for prognostic factors associated with adherence. Emulating a per-protocol design in an observational study mirrors a randomised controlled trial (RCT) but requires special consideration for time zero and additional adjustments for confounding at both baseline and follow-up stages. This comprehensive approach ensures that the analysis accurately reflects the real-world application of treatment strategies and provides reliable estimates of their effects.

2. Overview of LEADER trial

The LEADER trial (Liraglutide Effect and Action in Diabetes: Evaluation of Cardiovascular Outcome Results) was a significant clinical study designed to assess the long-term effects of liraglutide, a GLP-1 receptor agonist, on cardiovascular outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes at high risk of cardiovascular events. The primary aim was to determine whether liraglutide could reduce the incidence of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE), which include cardiovascular death, non-fatal myocardial infarction, or non-fatal stroke. Conducted over a median period of 3.8 years, the trial enrolled 9,340 participants across 32 countries, providing a robust data set for evaluating the efficacy and safety of liraglutide in this high-risk population.

The results of the LEADER trial were promising, demonstrating a significant reduction in the risk of MACE among participants treated with liraglutide compared to those receiving a placebo. Specifically, the trial found a 13% reduction in the primary composite endpoint of cardiovascular death, non-fatal myocardial infarction, or non-fatal stroke. Additionally, liraglutide was associated with a lower risk of death from cardiovascular causes by 22% and a reduction in all-cause mortality by 15%. These outcomes highlight liraglutide's potential not only in managing blood glucose levels but also in providing cardiovascular benefits, offering a dual advantage for patients with type 2 diabetes at a high Risk for cardiovascular [10].

Study design:

The LEADER trial was a multicentre, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial conducted at 410 sites in 32 countries. Patients with type 2 diabetes at high risk for cardiovascular disease were randomly assigned, in a 1:1 ratio, to receive the GLP-1 receptor agonist liraglutide or placebo. The minimum planned follow-up was 42 months, with a maximum of 60 months of receiving the assigned regimen and an additional 30 days of follow-up afterward[11].

The LEADER trial's inclusion criteria targeted patients with type 2 diabetes who had a glycated haemoglobin level of 7.0% or higher. Eligible participants either had not received previous treatment for diabetes or were on treatment with one or more oral antihyperglycemic agents, insulin (including human neutral protamine Hagedorn, long-acting analogues, or premixed insulins), or combinations of these agents. Additionally, participants needed to be 50 years or older with at least one cardiovascular coexisting condition such as coronary heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, peripheral vascular disease, chronic kidney disease stage 3 or greater, or chronic heart failure classified as New York Heart Association class II or III. Alternatively, those aged 60 years or older with at least one cardiovascular risk factor, such as microalbuminuria, proteinuria, hypertension with left ventricular hypertrophy, left ventricular systolic or diastolic dysfunction, or an ankle-brachial index of less than 0.9, were also eligible.

The exclusion criteria for the LEADER trial were stringent to ensure participant safety and data integrity. Patients with type 1 diabetes were excluded, as well as those using GLP-1 receptor agonists, dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP-4) inhibitors, pramlintide, or rapid-acting insulin. Additionally, individuals with a familial or personal history of multiple endocrine neoplasia type 2 or medullary thyroid cancer were not eligible. The trial also excluded patients who had experienced an acute coronary or cerebrovascular event within 14 days before the screening and randomization process. These criteria helped to create a well-defined study population and ensure that the trial results would be applicable to the appropriate patient demographic with type 2 diabetes at high cardiovascular risk.

Outcome:

The primary composite outcome in the time-to-event analysis was the first occurrence of death from cardiovascular causes, nonfatal myocardial infarction (including silent), or nonfatal stroke. Prespecified exploratory outcomes included an expanded composite cardiovascular outcome (comprising death from cardiovascular causes, nonfatal myocardial infarction, nonfatal stroke, coronary revascularization, or hospitalization for unstable angina pectoris or heart failure), death from any cause, and a composite renal and retinal microvascular outcome. The microvascular outcome encompassed nephropathy (new onset of macroalbuminuria, a doubling of serum creatinine with an eGFR of ≤ 45 ml/min/1.73 m², need for continuous renal-replacement therapy, or death from renal disease) and retinopathy (need for retinal photocoagulation or treatment with intravitreal agents, vitreous haemorrhages, or onset of diabetes-related blindness). Other outcomes included neoplasms and pancreatitis. All outcomes were adjudicated in a blinded manner by an independent external committee.[10]

Statistical analysis:

The primary and exploratory outcomes in the time-to-event analyses were assessed using a Cox proportional-hazards model with treatment as a covariate. The primary hypothesis tested whether liraglutide was noninferior to placebo regarding the primary outcome, with a noninferiority margin of 1.30 for the upper boundary of the 95% confidence interval of the hazard ratio. For exploratory outcomes, no adjustments were made for multiple comparisons. All randomised patients were included in the analyses, with data censored at their last visit if they completed or discontinued the trial without an outcome. Mean differences in glycated haemoglobin levels, weight, blood pressure, and pulse between trial groups were estimated using a mixed model for repeated measurements, adjusted for baseline covariates.[10]

3. Trial Emulation Study Design

3.1 Study population

We will use CPRD data to evaluate the cardiovascular disease outcomes of GLP-1 in individuals with type 2 diabetes with established cardiovascular disease. The CPRD was launched in 2012 by the UK Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) and the Department of Health's National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR). It was previously known as the Value Added Medical Products (VAMP) when established in 1987 followed by the General Practice Research Database (GPRD) from 1993, which were both smaller datasets. The CPRD dataset is now considered to be one of the largest sources of longitudinal primary care data in the world, comprised of anonymised electronic health record data collected every month by general practices in the UK. Patient information collected include data on demographics, clinical tests, diagnoses and treatments, referrals, behavioural factors and immunisations. Linked data from secondary care or other health-related data are also available in CPRD such as hospitalisation data (from Hospital Episode Statistics datasets), mortality data (from Office for National Statistics datasets) and deprivation data (from Index of Multiple Deprivation and Townsend scores datasets) [12].

3.2 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

To ensure that the target trial and the emulated trial using observational data are comparable, it is essential to establish a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria grounded in clinical expertise. This step is crucial for defining a consistent and relevant participant population, which minimises biases and enhances the validity of the comparisons. By carefully selecting criteria that align with those used in the target trial, we can ensure that the observational study population closely mirrors the clinical characteristics and risk profiles of the target trial participants. This alignment is vital for producing reliable and generalisable findings, ultimately contributing to more accurate assessments of the treatment effects being studied.

Table 1- Proposed Trial Emulation inclusion criteria using CPRD

	Emulation
<p>Type 2 diabetes</p> <p>Anti-diabetic drug naïve or treated with one or more oral anti-diabetic drugs or treated with human NPH insulin or long-acting insulin analogue or premixed insulin, alone or in combination with OAD(s).</p>	<p>Individuals with type 2 diabetes are included if they have a valid SNOMED code for type 2 diabetes in their electronic health record. Where there are inconsistencies in the type of diabetes recorded, the most recent type recorded by a specialist diabetes care provider will be used, if available. If the data have not been provided by a specialist diabetes provider, the most recent type of diabetes recorded in primary care will be used. Individuals with a diagnosis of heart failure who are treated only with SGLT2 inhibitors, as well as those receiving only liraglutide or semaglutide, are not considered to have type 2 diabetes.</p>
<p>Age \geq 50 at screening</p>	<p>Individuals aged 50 years or older when treatment of interest starts</p>
<p>Glycated haemoglobin \geq7.0%</p>	<p>HbA1c \geq 53 mmol/mol at the latest measurement before baseline, within a maximum of 1 year prior.</p>
<p>Prior cardiovascular disease cohort: age \geq50 and \geq1 of the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Prior MI ✓ Prior stroke or TIA ✓ Prior coronary, carotid or peripheral arterial revascularisation ✓ >50% stenosis of coronary, carotid, or lower extremity arteries ✓ History of symptomatic CHD documented by positive exercise stress test or any cardiac imaging or unstable angina with ECG changes ✓ Asymptomatic cardiac ischemia documented by positive nuclear imaging test, exercise test or dobutamine stress echo ✓ Chronic heart failure NYHA class II-III ✓ Chronic renal failure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • eGFR <60 mL/min/1.73m² (Modification of Diet in Renal Disease formula) • eGFR <60 mL/min (Cockcroft-Gault formula) 	<p>At least one admission to hospital for heart failure, hypertension, myocardial infarction, stroke, peripheral vascular disease or chronic kidney disease over the previous 10 years prior to the start of treatment or GFR < 60 ml/min/1.73m²</p>
<p>No Prior cardiovascular disease group: Age \geq60 y and \geq1 of the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Microalbuminuria or proteinuria ✓ Hypertension and left ventricular hypertrophy by ECG or imaging ✓ Left ventricular systolic or diastolic dysfunction by imaging ✓ Ankle-brachial index <0.9 	<p>On antihypertensive medication (beta blockers, ACEi, statins or calcium channel blockers) Hospital admission for diabetes foot ulcer.</p>

Table 2- Trial Emulation exclusion criteria using CPRD

Trial	Emulation
Type 1 diabetes	their most recent diagnosis of type 1 diabetes within 10 years before index
Calcitonin \geq50 ng/L	
Use of a GLP-1 receptor agonist (exenatide, liraglutide or other) or pramlintide or any DPP-4 inhibitor within the 3 months prior to screening	We will exclude use of DPP4 (Sitagliptin, Vildagliptin, Linagliptin) in the last 3 months
Use of insulin other than human NPH insulin or long-acting insulin analogue or premixed insulin within 3 months prior to screening. Short-term use of other insulin during this period in connection with intercurrent illness is allowed, at Investigator's discretion	Exclude insulin prescription in the last 3 months
Acute decompensation of glycaemic control	History of diabetic ketoacidosis (ICD-10: E11- E14) within 0-90 days before baseline.
Acute coronary or cerebrovascular event in the previous 14 days	Any occurrence of either the primary or secondary outcomes within 14 days before the index date
Currently planned coronary, carotid, or peripheral artery revascularisation	Not able to measure
Chronic heart failure (NYHA class IV)	Not applicable
Current continuous renal replacement therapy	Patients on dialysis (ICD-10: Z99.2) within 180 days before the index date
End-stage liver disease	History of liver failure (ICD-10: K72) within 0-10 years before baseline
History of solid organ transplant or awaiting solid organ transplant	History of organ or tissue transplant (ICD-10: Z94) within 0-10 years before baseline
Malignant neoplasm	History of any cancer diagnosis excluding non-melanoma skin cancer (ICD-10 codes C00-C97) within 0-10 years before baseline
Family or personal history of multiple endocrine neoplasia type 2 or familial medullary thyroid carcinoma	Personal history of multiple endocrine neoplasia (ICD-10: D44.8) within 0-10 years before baseline
Personal history of non-familial medullary thyroid carcinoma	History of malignant neoplasm of thyroid gland (ICD-10: C73) within 0-10 years before baseline

4. Study duration and follow-ups

In the emulation study, we will encompass data from the timeframe of Mid-2017 to 2022/3. This period allows for a minimum of one year of follow-up after the initial prescription redemption, with a retrospective look back of up to 10 years from baseline to define covariates and inclusion/exclusion criteria.

For this study, "time zero" is defined as the first instance a patient redeems a prescription for one of the medications of interest, while also meeting all inclusion and exclusion criteria within the specified timeframe. This approach ensures that patients are appropriately categorised based on their medication history and clinical status leading up to their inclusion in the study.

5. Treatment of interest

In the LEADER trial, patients underwent a 2-week placebo run-in phase to ensure they could adhere to the injection regimen. Following this phase, they were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive either 1.8 mg of liraglutide (or the maximum tolerated dose) or a placebo once daily as a subcutaneous injection, alongside standard care. The trial's ethical justification for using a placebo control included strict criteria for patient discontinuation, the ability to adjust background treatments to achieve glucose and HbA1c goals, and guidelines for rescue therapy. In our emulation of the trial, we designate DPP-4 inhibitors as the active comparator of interest due to their hypothesised neutral effects on cardiovascular outcomes.

The aim of trial emulation is to primarily “compare taking GLP-1 receptor agonists continuously during the follow-up, unless otherwise clinically indicated with continuous treatment with DPP-4 inhibitors unless otherwise clinically indicated”. Our approach involves using a discrete time scale with intervals of six months. Patients will be considered "on treatment" within a specific time interval if they redeemed at least one prescription during that interval. This method allows us to simulate real-world treatment scenarios and assess comparative effectiveness over time between these two classes of medications.

6. Outcome(s)

Table 3 - Primary and Secondary Outcomes in LEADER Trial and Emulation

Trial	Emulation
Primary endpoint	
First occurrence of cardiovascular death, nonfatal myocardial infarction, or nonfatal stroke (a composite cardiovascular outcome)	First occurrence of cardiovascular death, nonfatal myocardial infarction, or nonfatal stroke.
Secondary endpoints	
First occurrence of an expanded composite cardiovascular outcome, defined as either cardiovascular death, non-fatal myocardial infarction, non-fatal stroke, revascularisation, unstable angina, or hospitalisation for chronic heart failure	First occurrence of one of the following outcomes: myocardial infarction, stroke, revascularisation, unstable angina, new diagnosis of heart failure, cardiovascular death
All-cause mortality	All-cause mortality
Each component of the composite cardiovascular outcome	Each component of the composite cardiovascular outcome

7. Variable selection

Explicitly emulating a target trial alone cannot eliminate the bias that arises from the lack of randomisation, such as confounding from noncomparable treatment groups. Even if the observational analysis accurately emulates all other components of the target trial, confounding remains a significant challenge. To address this, successful target trial emulation requires detailed data not only on treatment and outcomes but also on potential confounders.

Some sources of routinely collected data, such as administrative claims databases, may provide reasonably detailed information on treatments and outcomes but often lack sufficient data on clinical factors that need adjustment. This limitation can hinder the ability to control for confounding effectively. The key advantage of a correct target trial emulation is that it eliminates other common sources of bias, allowing researchers to concentrate on addressing confounding. By ensuring detailed and comprehensive data collection on confounders, alongside treatments and outcomes, the emulation can more accurately approximate the conditions of a randomised trial, thus improving the validity of the causal inferences drawn from the observational study[4].

To select the adequate variables for adjustment in our target trial emulation, we will use the disjunctive cause criterion[13]. This criterion posits that sufficient control for confounding can be achieved by choosing as confounders those variables that are causes of the exposure or outcome or both, then, additionally, discarding any variable known to be an instrumental variable, and including variables that do not satisfy the criterion but are good proxies for unmeasured common causes of the exposure and the outcome [13].

8. Potential confounders

We will categorise variables into two groups: pre-treatment variables and time-varying variables. Pre-treatment and baseline variables will be evaluated at baseline or up to 10 years preceding baseline to adjust for confounding factors existing before treatment initiation. Time-varying variables will be updated over the study period to accommodate changes that could influence treatment outcomes. Co-medication will be defined by reviewing the 180 days leading up to baseline, while the history of long-term conditions will encompass the 10 years preceding baseline. These approaches will help ensure a comprehensive assessment and robust comparison between continuous treatments with GLP-1 and DPP4 inhibitors.

Table 4 - Potential confounders

Pre-treatment and baseline variable	Time-varying variables
Age (continuous)	
Sex (male, female or unspecified)	
Index of multiple deprivation (calculated from each individuals postcode)	
Duration of diabetes (categorised as 0-5, 5-10, >10 years)	
Smoking (Yes/No)	Smoking (Yes/No)
HbA1c (continuous), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	HbA1c (continuous)
Cholesterol (continuous), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	
Blood pressure (continuous), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	
Glomerular filtration rate based on creatinine (eGFR), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	Glomerular filtration rate based on creatinine (eGFR)
BMI	BMI
Concomitant glucose lowering treatment	Adding SGLT2i / Insulin
History of atrial fibrillation	Incident of atrial fibrillation
History of Ischemic heart disease	Incident of Ischemic heart disease
History of myocardial infarction	Incident of myocardial infarction
History of heart failure	Incident of heart failure
History of stroke	Incident of stroke
History of peripheral artery disease	Incident of peripheral artery disease
History of renal disease	Incident of renal disease
History of diabetic eye disease	Incident of diabetic eye disease
History of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	Incident of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
History of hypertension	Incident of hypertension
Therapy with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Aldosterone receptor antagonists ✓ Beta-blockers ✓ Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers ✓ Loop diuretics ✓ Calcium channel blockers ✓ Thiazide diuretics ✓ Acetylsalicylic acid (aspirin) ✓ Statins 	Therapy with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Aldosterone receptor antagonists ✓ Beta-blockers ✓ Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers ✓ Loop diuretics ✓ Calcium channel blockers ✓ Thiazide diuretics ✓ Acetylsalicylic acid (aspirin) ✓ Statins

9. Data preparation

We will explore the distribution of all continuous variables using relevant measures and graphs, such as measures of central tendency and variation, box plots, histograms, and Q-Q plots, to identify outliers. Any outliers found will be checked to determine if they are clinically plausible or if they are due to measurement error.

To address missing data, we will check the mechanism of missingness using formal tests like Little's MCAR test and graphical methods, such as heatmap plots. For data imputation, we will use random forest -based methods i.e. Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations Random Forest (MICE RF)[14]). Studies have shown that this method is suitable for complex epidemiological studies and can produce unbiased estimates of (log) hazard ratios. Parameter estimates are less biased using random forest MICE, and confidence interval coverage is improved[15].

10. Analysis

10.1 Target parameter of interest

Comparing taking GLP-1 receptor agonists continuously during the follow-up, unless otherwise clinically indicated with continuous treatment with DPP-4 inhibitors unless otherwise clinically indicated.

For supplementary analyses, we are interested in the same contrast at 1,2,3, and 5 years.

10.2 Descriptive analysis

Initially, we will calculate summary statistics for both continuous and categorical variables. Continuous variables will be described using measures of central tendency such as mean and median, and measures of dispersion like standard deviation and interquartile range. Categorical variables will be summarised with frequencies and percentages.

Baseline characteristics will be compared between treatment groups using appropriate statistical tests to assess the balance before treatment initiation. Additionally, we will provide a detailed summary of the use of GLP-1 inhibitors and DPP4 inhibitors, both as initial and time-varying treatments, and the incidence of primary and secondary outcomes across treatment groups. For time-varying variables, incidence rates over time will be calculated, and Kaplan-Meier curves will visualise time-to-event data for key outcomes. After performing multiple imputations, we will compare the distribution of imputed data with the original data to ensure that imputation has not introduced bias. These descriptive analyses will provide a solid foundation for the subsequent inferential analyses, ensuring that any findings are based on a thorough understanding of the data.

To capture changes in HbA1c levels over time, we will use longitudinal graphs. These graphs will display the trends in HbA1c for both medication groups, highlighting how glycaemic control evolves during the study period. Furthermore, we will analyse prescription patterns and treatment adherence using longitudinal data. Graphs will show the frequency of treatment dropouts and switches, providing insights into patient adherence and the sustainability of each treatment strategy. These visualisations will enable us to identify common reasons for discontinuation and assess whether patients who switch treatments exhibit different clinical outcomes compared to those who remain on their initial medication.

10.3 Longitudinal Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (LTMLE)

We will employ a discrete time scale with periods of six months ($t=0, 6, 12, \dots, 60$) to estimate the target parameters using a longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimator (LTMLE). LTMLE is a robust statistical method that accounts for time-varying covariates and treatments, providing accurate and unbiased causal effect estimates [16, 17].

Our data will be structured into 6-month intervals, creating a longitudinal dataset where each participant has multiple records corresponding to each 6-month period. Each record will include both time-varying covariates (e.g., HbA1c levels, incident health conditions, concomitant medications) and treatment status for that interval. Baseline covariates such as age, sex, and initial health conditions will be included as static variables.

LTMLE updates an initial sequential regression estimator using inverse probability weighting, accounting for the propensity of treatment and the probability of not being censored using Super Learner approach. SL is an ensemble method that allows researchers to combine several different prediction algorithms into one where the candidate algorithms can be quite different. It uses K-fold cross-validation to build the optimally weighted combination of predictions from a library of candidate machine learning algorithms[18, 19].The estimation procedure involves several key steps:

Model Specification:

Define models for the treatment mechanism (the probability of receiving GLP-1 versus DPP4 inhibitors given past covariates and treatment history) and the outcome mechanism (the probability of the outcome given past covariates and treatment history).

Initial Estimates:

Obtain initial estimates of the outcome and treatment probabilities using these models. All nuisance parameter regression models necessary for the initial estimator and for the targeting step will be adjusted for additive effects of all covariates updated to the current time interval, ensuring the causal time order of the variables is maintained.

Targeted Update:

Apply a targeting step to adjust the initial estimates using inverse probability weights. Specifically, we will regress the outcome, treatment, and censoring variables defined in the calendar time interval (t, t+6 months) on the most recent values of the time-dependent covariates at time t and the entire history of the treatment variables up to time t.

Penalised Ridge Regression:

Fit all nuisance parameter models using penalised ridge regression, selecting penalty parameters to under smooth the regression fits, which helps in reducing the bias in the estimates.

Iterative Process:

The targeting step is iterated until the estimates converge, ensuring the final estimates are consistent with the observed data and the specified causal model.

Reporting and Interpretation:

The primary analysis will focus on estimating the causal effect of taking GLP-1 receptor agonists continuously during the follow-up, unless otherwise clinically indicated with continuous treatment with DPP-4 inhibitors unless otherwise clinically indicated. the study period. We will report the longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimates (LTMLE) with 95% confidence intervals. These estimates will provide robust and interpretable causal insights into the comparative effectiveness of GLP-1 inhibitors and DPP4 inhibitors in real-world clinical practice.

By employing LTMLE, we address the complexities of time-varying treatments and covariates, ensuring that our analysis correctly models the dynamic nature of treatment effects and confounding factors over time. This approach will yield reliable and nuanced insights into the long-term impacts of these diabetes treatments.

10.4 Subgroup and sensitivity analysis

In line with the subgroup analysis conducted in the LEADER trial and ensuring an adequate sample size, we will stratify our analysis of the primary and secondary outcomes across several key

demographic and clinical subgroups. These subgroups include sex, age group, baseline HbA1c levels, duration of diabetes, and history of a previous cardiovascular event. By examining treatment effects within these subpopulations, we aim to identify potential variations in treatment response and assess the generalisability of our findings across diverse patient profiles.

As part of our sensitivity analysis, we will implement a grace period of 30 days by shifting the index date to day 30 after treatment initiation. This adjustment allows for a more flexible definition of treatment exposure, accounting for potential delays in treatment response or adherence variations during the initial phase of therapy. Following the adjustment, we will repeat our main analysis, including the estimation of primary and secondary outcomes, within this modified timeframe[20].

10.5 supplementary analysis

We will expand our analysis to evaluate treatment regimens in populations excluded from the original trials. In addition to emulation, we will conduct a parallel analysis in a broader population with less stringent inclusion and exclusion criteria, such as those without cardiovascular disease and without age restrictions (>50/60 years), assessing outcomes across the same and additional subgroups specified in the trials. Furthermore, we will replicate the primary outcome measure at intervals of 1, 2, 3, and 5 years to provide a comprehensive evaluation over time.

11. Appendix

Table A1- Medication types

Medication	ATC code
Mineralocorticoids	N/A
Beta-blocker	Yes
Renin-angiotensin system inhibitor	Yes
Loop diuretics	Yes
Calcium channel blockers	No
Thiazide	Yes
Acetylsalicylic acid (Aspirin)	No
Statin	Yes

Table A2- Medical condition definitions

Medical condition	ICD-10
Heart failure	I50.1, I50.20-23, I50.30-33, I50.40-43, I50.9
Hypertension*	I10, I11, I11.0, I1.9
Ischemic heart disease	I121.0-9, I122.0-9, I20.0-9, I24, 02703ZZ, 02713ZZ, 02723ZZ, 02733ZZ, 02763ZZ, 02773ZZ, 02783ZZ, 02793ZZ, 02793ZZ
Stroke	I61.0-9, I63.0-9, I166, I169
Peripheral vascular disease	I170.20-29
Chronic renal disease	N18.3-5, E10.2, E11.2
Atrial fibrillation	I48.0, I48.1, I48.11, I48.11, I48.19, I482, 21, 3,4,91, 92, I44.91, 92,
Cancer, except non-melanoma skin cancer	C00-C14, C15-26, C30-39, C40-41, C43-58, C60-97
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	J40, J43, J44
Myocardial infarction	I121.0-9, I122.0-9
Revascularization	02703ZZ, 02713ZZ, 02723ZZ, 02733ZZ, 02763ZZ, 02773ZZ, 02783ZZ, 02793ZZ, 02793ZZ
Unstable angina	I20.0-9, I24

Table A3: ATC codes to define glucose-lowering drug classes

Medication class	ATC code
Insulin	Z79.84
Biguanide	Z79.84
Metformin	Z79.84
Sulfonylurea	Z79.84
Alfa glucosidase inhib	Z79.84
Thiazolidinedione (Glitazones)	Z79.84
DPP4 inhibitors	Z79.84
SGLT2 inhibitors	Z79.84
GLP1-RA	Z79.84

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